

SIGNIFICANCE OF SOME SPECIES BELONGING TO DARKLING BEETLES IN NATURE AND AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *In this article, the importance of the species belonging to the Tenebrionidae family in nature and in agriculture was studied by analyzing some of the studies conducted by scientists in this regard.*

Keywords: *tenebrionidae, darkling beetles, eleodes, pests.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada olimlarning bu borada olib borgan ayrim tadqiqotlari tahlil qilinib, Tenebrionidae oilasiga mansub turlarning tabiatdagi va qishloq xo‘jaligidagi ahamiyati o‘rganildi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *tenebrionidae, qoratanli qo‘ng‘iz, eleodes, zararkunanda.*

The family Tenebrionidae, known as darkling beetles, is characterized by a high species composition and ecological diversity and plays an important role in the decomposition of organic matter and nutrient cycling in the soil. The significance of tenebrionids in decomposing dead organic becomes more considerable from north to south in Asia in proportion to increasing aridity [1]. Some of them act as pests of agricultural crops in agroecosystems [2, 3, 4, 5], while another group feeds on stored grain products and damages them [6]. In addition, darkling beetles are an important and integral part of the system of trophic relations. Despite the fact that most members of the family have protective glands, they have been recorded in the diets of more than 200 species of mammals, birds, reptiles, amphibians and arthropods [1]. In some arid areas, tenebrionids are the main food of local carnivores [7].

Their larvae are phytophagous insects, called false wireworms, and most species live in pastures. Planting agricultural crops increases their food supply. Therefore, any young seedlings can be damaged or destroyed by them. It was found that false wireworms feed on oilseeds, grain legumes and cereals. They significantly affect cultivated areas. Sometimes crops can be replanted in affected areas. Damage can be noticeable when larger false wireworms reach up to 5 per square meter in dry conditions. Small larvae also feed on plant seedlings, but their damage is not significant. The damage of false wireworms is greatest when plant germination is slowed due to lack of moisture [8]. Mature larvae of some species normally do not pose a threat to fall-seeded grains because feeding at that stage is insignificant [9]. We can meet representatives of this family in cultivated fields in all regions where agricultural practices are used. Their larval period varies depending on humidity and temperature. Adult tenebrionids in desert zone may live up to seven years [1].

Desert darkling beetles feed mainly on plants and make up the majority of the entomofauna, not only in terms of species diversity, but also in terms of biomass [10]. The damage of darkling beetles to plants is especially noticeable in the spring months. For example, in desert regions, one individual of the giant darkling beetle (*Pisterotarsa gigantea*) can eat up to 5-7 buds of woody plants in one day. When their density reaches 2000 individuals per hectare, they can destroy up to 20 000 developing plants. Darkling beetles are mainly polyphagous insects, feeding on vegetative parts of living plants, their seeds in the soil, dead plants, rotting plant debris, mycelium of soil fungi, and insect corpses and remains [11]. Only some species are specialized in the type of food. Representatives of the genera *Eleodes* and *Blapstinus* feed on

plant roots in agrocenoses, and they have great economic value. Species belonging to the genera *Tribolium*, *Gnathocerus*, *Palorus*, *Sitophilus* and *Latheticus* are pests of stored cereals. Such species are called secondary pests and are distributed throughout the world [6]. Some of the synanthropic species are stored food pests, while others are important in spreading disease-causing microorganisms and the eggs of parasitic helminths. Such species include *Cyphogenia lucifuga*, *Atrachyderma setosa*, *Bllethifera pterotapha*, *Blaps deplanata* [12].

According to Quiroga-Murcia and Posada-Flórez (2013), *E. pos. omissoides* larvae feed on seeds of plant species such as corn, peas, and wheat. They also attack germinating seeds, damaging the seed coat and sometimes the apical part of the primary root. This in turn leads to the formation of secondary roots and delays the growth of maize and peas [13]. Calkins and Kirk (1973) evaluated *E. suturalis* damage and found that 100% of germinating sugar beet, 95.9% of oat, 71.6% of wheat, and 26.4% of soybean seed were infected in greenhouses [14]. Only one species of the genus *Eleodes* (*Eleodes longicollis punctigerus*) can damage 15-72% of newly transplanted tomato plants [3]. As a result of the analysis of the digestive system of 13 species of the genus *Eleodes*, it was found that there are 47 types of plants in their diet. It is 15% Poaceae, 70% weeds, and the rest are plants belonging to various botanic families [15]. Species of the genus *Blastinus* are pests of plants in the imago and larval stages. The damage of these beetles to pepper, wheat and strawberry plants has been determined [16]. In addition, it feeds on young seedlings, flowers, leaf tissues and ripe fruits of crops belonging to the Cucurbitaceae. Despite the fact that these insects are mainly melon pests, they can also be found in watermelon fields [17].

Opatrum sabulosum can be included among species that feed on cultivated and wild grasses and damage crops. When the diet of this species was studied in laboratory conditions, it was found that they consumed 95,5% of the selected cultivated plants and 48,5% of the uncultivated plants. According to the results of the research, the cultivated plants which have the highest consumption rate are *Perilla nankinensis*, *Lycopersicon esculentum*, *Tropaeolum majus*, *Nicotiana tabacum*, *Rumex acetosa* and *Beta vulgaris*.

In recent years, species belonging to the Tenebrionidae family have been found to be entering new agrocenoses. In 2020, the larvae of the subspecies *Opatroides punctulatus subcylindricus*, which was recorded for the first time in Turkey, fed on the leaves and graft buds of pistachio seedlings, and it was found that they infected 68.3% of the pistachio orchards [5]. It is recorded that this species overwinters on melon, pumpkin, soybeans, cotton, tobacco, cereals, young seedlings, vines, and mulberries. They, in turn, can harm these plants [18, 19].

In conclusion, darkling beetles are important in nature in the decomposition of organic matter in soil and as an important part of the food chain. In addition, they are considered pests of agricultural crops and stored grain products. *Eleodes* and *Blapstinus* genera may cause serious damage to seeds and seedlings of different plant species.

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